

Project Title:	Linking homeless children and their families to community health and wellbeing services: Using a Nurse Practitioner model of care to improve child health outcomes.
EOI Ref No.:	15536490
Chief Investigator:	Dr Yvonne K Parry

BACKGROUND – Word limit: 1600

In Australia 1.1 million children live in poverty/disadvantage [1, 2], with an additional 22% of all Australian children living in housing instability [48]. The exposure to a cycle of disadvantage has lifelong effects [3-17]. Disadvantaged/vulnerable children have poorer access to health services, lower medical appointment compliance, increased Emergency Department (ED) utilisation, and overall poorer health outcomes [9 -12, 16-23]. Current models of health service delivery do not meet the health needs of children and families facing adversity, vulnerability, and homelessness/housing instability [3-8]. While the homelessness sector does provide health care, these services target rough sleepers. Homeless families with children 0-18 tend not to use these services [43, 67]. Without access to health care developmental milestones may be missed. These families fall through the gaps in health service delivery, resulting in poor social, educational, and healthcare outcomes [6-10, 24].

Children from homeless families often suffer long term physical and mental health impacts from disadvantage. Adverse childhood experiences incurred during times of disadvantage include trauma, domestic violence, and multiple toxic stressors that negatively impact long term on neurobiological development, cognitive ability, and mental health [3-6, 10-14, 39]. Children from disadvantaged backgrounds have higher rates of acute and chronic health conditions including otitis media, asthma, scabies, respiratory infections, gastroenteritis, anxiety, and depression [3-7]. In addition, children living in homeless families endure 6-times the rates of injury and accidents, are 3-times more likely to have poor health, and lower rates of immunisation [3-7].

Current forms of health access do not adequately meet the needs of children in families who experience homelessness/housing instability increasing the prevalence of accumulative harm and long-term deleterious health outcomes. For example, it is known that children between the ages of 0 to 12 years make up 25% of the homeless population in Australia[4-6]; their poorer health, educational and social outcomes are partly explained by their disconnection from the usual health and service provision that optimises child development and mitigates adverse childhood experiences[8, 40]. Every day, 2 in every 3 homeless children (0-12 years) who require immediate accommodation from homeless services are turned away [4].

Ad hoc care, such as Emergency Department use, during childhood can result in inconsistent, inappropriate, and detrimentally longer-term health outcomes. Emergency only care can result in missed immunisation, physical, cognitive and behavioural developmental impairment and failure to meet milestones, due to missing educational and health appointments[1-8, 18-22] that would address deleterious health, education and social impacts of disadvantage. Additionally, the use of Emergency Departments can impact on the sustainability of publicly provided healthcare [19]. Australian Emergency Department expenditure was \$4.7 billion, up 13.4% on the year prior (2015-2016) with the 2017-18 expenditure increasing by a further 3.4% [19]. Associated increasing morbidity and mortality is linked to delays in Emergency Department care and poorly targeted processes [19-23]. Further, while the population under the age of 4 accounts for only 7% of the total Australian population, it represents 11% of all current Emergency Department presentations [19]. Previous research found that up to 76% of paediatric presentations were for primary healthcare issues [18-23]. Australian and international research states disadvantaged, and vulnerable children and their parents are more likely to use paediatric ED for primary health care [18-23]. This research aims to address this current detrimental inappropriate under-servicing.

A major problem in addressing appropriate health access is the lack of data on the health needs of children in housing instability/homelessness. For example, homelessness services were not mandated to count children attending with a parent until 2009 in South Australia and 2014 in NSW[16, 24 43, 44] making knowledge of the number of children exposed to this type of disadvantage only recent. Additionally, homeless-services are often the

first to know when children are at risk of abuse or neglect and disconnected from other services [17, 23-28, 38]. Targeted interventions, such as the proposed Nurse Practitioner (NP) 'Health-Navigator' model of care, provides not only immediate health interventions but can help reduce longer term negative health outcomes of childhood homelessness [1-13]. Our 2019, pilot project captured the rates of missed care with 70% of attending children linked into to GP, Specialists, Optometry, audiology, and Allied health care services [43].

A innovative, embedded, self-funded (Medicare) Nurse Practitioner health intervention will address the deficits in current health access, through in-depth assessments of health needs, treatment plans, referrals to appropriate health, support referral compliance and parental education on developmental health checks. The NP led models of care have been effective in addressing missed care for disadvantaged/vulnerable populations but have not addressed children in homelessness [29-38, 41,42]. Our pilot study proved families with children aged 0-12 can benefit from enhanced access to health care, social support and increase uptake of referrals leading to improved child health outcomes [46].

Nurse Practitioners are educationally prepared at Masters Degree level with specialist knowledge, post-graduate education and skills, and have the authority to use extended practice privileges to make informed and autonomous decisions on preventative, diagnostic and therapeutic management, such as antibiotic prescriptions, x-ray, CT scans and direct medical and specialist referrals [29-38, 41,42] well beyond the current levels of services provided in the homelessness sector for children and families[3, 7, 8, 25-28]. This proposed research builds on a working partnership between Flinders University (CIA) and a not-for-profit community provider Uniting Care Wesley Bowden (UCWB) to implement and evaluate an innovative Nurse Practitioner (NP) model of care. The data collection functions, and referral tracking are research specific activities covered by the research funds and are key to evaluating the service (see diagram below).

The child's journey through the NP 'health navigator' model of care

The child's pathway, the responsive and purposeful feedback loop used is mapped above. Building on international randomized controlled trials (RCT) nurse-led interventions [29-35], this study targets the most vulnerable childhood

populations in the community to expand the services supporting the child and the family. The NP led referrals and support of the child and family will add to the care, education, and health options available to provide broader support. This will assist in effectively mitigating the child's potential exposure to child protection notifications, mental health issues and will improve our knowledge on effective and broader linked interventions for the 1.1 million children in Australia living in disadvantage [2].

Nurse Practitioners (NP) are ideally situated to undertake this cost effective [29-35] innovative model of health service delivery. NP models of care use a combination of nursing care, diagnostic activities, and intervention-based treatments, including the use of medicines [29-35]. Therefore, the evaluation of the NP 'Health-Navigator' model aims to:

- Mitigate previous missed care opportunities.
- Providing holistic, advanced, and comprehensive assessments.
- Increase acuity of care to meet complex health and social needs.
- Extend collaborative care services e.g. longer support and consultation/treatment times.
- Support interdisciplinary referrals for the multimodal interventions required by children.
- Provide targeted appropriate child focused primary care thus mitigating the use of emergency departments for primary care.

Nurse Practitioners are well positioned to provide targeted and in-depth health care to complex families and vulnerable populations who might otherwise use the Emergency Department or have missed care. Care of vulnerable populations and those living in disadvantage support the use of NP as it is a cost-effective model of care [29-35]. NP care is highly valued by patient's when measured using scoring tools [29-35].

Nurse practitioners advanced educational preparation and specialist knowledge and skills and the use of extended Medicare practice privileges allows them to provide a broader Social Determinants of Health informed level of care [29-35] when caring for complex health issues in vulnerable populations[29-35]. The NP assessment will inform the referral to primary care using the NP direct service links to local GPs. The NP in the NGO sector are also perfectly placed to monitor referral compliance.

Targeted interventions provide not only immediate relief but reduce longer term negative health outcomes. The 12-month period of data collection will provide an in-depth snapshot of each family's needs and evaluate the service up-take and outcomes. This type of data collection and supportive intervention process is necessary for families dealing with complex life circumstances while aligning with three of the Channel 7 research priority areas. The involvement of an internationally renowned team will enable the embedding and expansion of the health service delivery model to other sites state-wide and nationally through our partnerships with other NGOs engaged in this work, Uniting Care Wesley Bowden, and the Nurse Practitioners Associations. Our community partners at UCWB are keen to support, disseminate and implement the use of the NP care model nationally once it is evidence based. Internationally the numbers of children living in housing instability have increased by 70% in the last decade [45, 67]. This project provides up-scalable and transferable outcomes that can be disseminated actively internationally via publications, keynote speaker (ACCYPN), conference presentations and publications.

This proposal provides proof of concept, building on our scoping project, conducted in 2019 that found the children had; low immunisation rates, only 11% were appropriately fully immunised; high rates of health conditions, such as chronic dental caries, Craniosynostosis, significant Plagiocephaly, severe motor delay, developmental delay, with 66% of the children requiring immediate interventions, and 44% assessed as having severe conditions[46]. The NP actioned referrals to GP, Optometry, Surgical interventions (ENT), Audiology, Physiotherapy, Psychotherapy and Dentistry. Additionally, 44% identified as being Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander [46]. The NP provided 75% of families with home visits due to lack of transport and the impact of COVID-19 restrictions [46]. Without a NP intervention in the homeless-service, these children would remain disconnected from health and wellbeing services including education. This nurse-led service requires robust evaluation to identify outcomes, barriers, and facilitators of the model in order to roll out the service nationally. The research proposal addresses this need.

Expand on the answer given in the Expression of Interest; note word limits:

This study is a collaborative community and consumer driven project that aims to evaluate and meet the complex health needs of vulnerable children living in housing instability. The proposed study uses a concurrent mixed methods design, with the NP as a 'Health-Navigator' [28, 49, 50, 63]. A mixed methods design is appropriate for three reasons. Firstly, investigating health access requires a technique that utilises both quantitative and qualitative methods in order to capture the diverse reasons for use, non-use or non-compliance of health and social services. Secondly, the World Health Organisation (WHO) recommends the use of mixed methods for researching the Social Determinants of Health and health access [28, 46-50, 59]. Finally, mixed method increases the robustness of the research process by triangulating the results through multiple methods and sources of information [28, 59]. Additionally, this project builds on a long-term working partnership between the CIA and a not-for-profit community provider, Inner Southern Homelessness Service (part of UCWB) to introduce, assess and evaluate an innovative NP model of care.

The study aims are met through 4 stages:

The diagram below outlines the four stages of the concurrent mixed methods and data collection sequence.

Concurrent methods diagram:

The diagram above outlines the assessment process in the research plan. Funding is not being requested to pay the salary of the Nurse Practitioner. This is covered under Medicare. Only research activities carried out by the NP are required within the grant bid, along with funding for the Research Associate.

Stage 1: Nurse Practitioner comprehensive assessment:

1.1 Using the comprehensive health assessment tool, (those trialled in the scoping study [46] were based on the WHO child assessment tool [65], and the extensive NP paediatric training [18, 28, 59]. The NP will measure the levels of health need in children accessing homelessness services expanding our current knowledge (Aim 1).

1.2 The de-identified nominal measures and condition severity scores are added to the data collection tool (piloted in 2019, NP research data collection is not a Medicare funded activity). The Research Associate (RA) will prepare and analyse the data, and a statistician will conduct the structural equation modelling (SEM) and odds ratio analysis. Quantitative data collection: age of child, the presenting condition, severity of condition, immunization status, Treatment by NP, Aboriginal Torres Strait Islander or Refugee identity, referral provided, usual health access, difficulties in appointment attendance, and the need for NP home visit e.g. parental agoraphobia or anxiety is collected [22, 47] as it demonstrates a barrier to child health assess (Aim 1 and 2).

Stage 2: Monitoring of Referral compliance and pathway

2.1 Using the developed NP referral pathway and tracking measures (the USAID Referral Systems Assessment and Monitoring Toolkit) [22, 47], following the referral, the children and families will be linked to GP primary health, allied health, and acute care services (covered by Medicare). A feedback loop from referral partners measuring compliance e.g. hospital admission, GP use, optometry, audiology etc data will be collected (Aim 1 and 2).

2.2 Establishment of the Research Reference Group (RRG) at ISHS (Aim 1, 2 and 3).

Stage 3: Qualitative evaluation

3.1 To determine the effectiveness of the NP intervention the RA will conduct 30 semi-structured qualitative interviews and 10 case study reviews. Drawing on the expertise of the RRG, 20 families receiving the NP intervention (pool of 250), and further 10 staff/managers from the homeless-service will invited to be interviewed and 10 case studies will be randomly selected for audit of health outcomes of the NP intervention (Aim 3).

3.2 Barriers and facilitators to health access including the use of the NP 'Health-Navigator' service will be identified (Aim 1 and 2).

The qualitative data will be thematically analysed for dominant themes.

Stage 4: Quantitative Family evaluation

One hundred (100) families will be invited to complete the post NP intervention evaluation questionnaire using the validated International Nurse Practitioner Satisfaction Survey [47] (first time used in Australia) the Post NP Intervention)) has Cronbach alpha rating of 0.9 internationally (Aims 1, 2 and 3).

Findings from these two consumer data sources (20 parent and staff interviews and 10 case studies) will be triangulated with the post NP-led survey results. Data will add to the structured equation modelling analysis [57].

The intervention/evaluation reflects the complexity and depth of the unmet need in these children. The CIA and her team have conducted several extensive service delivery evaluations using correlations, SEM and odds ratio (the effect of a variable on the likelihood that an outcome will occur) along with qualitative thematic and narrative analysis comparable to this proposed project [8, 18, 25, 26, 28, 38, 46, 54-59]. This single arm before (the NP maps current health access levels) and after study will track the children and families and measure the change in referral uptake and health outcomes over the length of time they engage with the homeless-service. The families (>250 per month) are usually engaged between 6-12 months and have had no or limited access to health services except ED prior to arrival at the homeless-service. Therefore, interventions need to be embedded, targeted, supported and timely and the NP and extensive collaborations with the community partner ISHS will facilitate these actions. Nurse Practitioners are well positioned to provided targeted and in-depth health care to complex families and vulnerable populations who might otherwise use the Emergency Department or have missed care. This nurse-led service requires robust evaluation to identify outcomes, barriers, and facilitators of the model to roll out the service nationally.

Data analysis

The SEM is a theory-driven analytical approach to priori specified hypothesis between measurable and/or latent variables [57-59]. The relations between variables using SEM provides a pictorial representation of the observed factors/variables in the research with the modelling of the independent variable (referral uptake/compliance) impacts on the other variables: presenting condition (severity), connectedness, such as: education, health service use, immunisation rates, with variable such as length of homelessness and transport. SEM relates levels of connectedness of each variable to the next [57-59]. This describes the relations between the variables and the impact of several variables on the variable of interest (independent variable). These measures and analysis will accurately capture the impact of the intervention across several areas of the child's development and health needs. This will inform practical useability and outcomes of the model of service delivery.

In conjunction with the SEM analysis described above the interviews provide the parents and staff the opportunity to represent themselves within the health delivery system and how they see their empowerment and self-determination in accessing services for their children. An analysis of the reoccurring themes will provide an in-depth understanding of the parents and staff views on the effectiveness and role of the NP as a 'Health-Navigator' and highlights areas for improvement. A comparison on the main themes from all the interviews provides a triangulation and summary of the interview data. This provides a consumer and service provider voice on the current limits of the health services and health care available to these children. This ensures the purposeful nature of the research project and its responsiveness to meet the needs of this population. Previous research with this population has identified the enthusiasm of parents to be involved and heard. This research provides a voice for homeless parents and children.

Additionally, this project builds on a long-term working partnership between the university nursing staff (CIA) and a not-for-profit community provider, Inner Southern Homelessness Service (part of UCWB) to introduce, assess and evaluate an innovative NP model of care (Diagram 1 below) [43]. Intervention logic model processes (Diagram 1) provide concise project plans that measure activities to matched outcomes.

Diagram 1: Nurse Practitioner intervention logic model.

Diagram 1: Nurse Practitioner intervention logic model process

Adapted from: WHO/CDC LOGIC MODEL FOR INTERVENTIONS IN PUBLIC HEALTH

The intervention logic model process above (Diagram 1) [51-60, 64] and the internationally robust and validated tools used in this project will determine the program deliverables, essential for the improvement of health outcomes for children facing disadvantage/vulnerabilities, such as homelessness. Using SEM, odds ratio, and

narrative analysis techniques provides the best synthesis of the effectiveness of the model [28, 51-60]. The research addresses the UN Sustainable Development Goals: 3 and 10.

The project aligns with three of the CRF priority research areas; a) Improving children's mental health and the impact of developmental disorders; b) Understanding the social determinants of childhood health and development, and c) Improving child protection and its effects.

The intensive mixed methods evaluation using triangulated data methods will enable the research team to explore in depth the processes involved in supporting disadvantaged (homeless) children and their families to adhere to referrals and improve referral outcomes, along with identifying the barriers involved in referral uptake. Referral uptake is impacted by health inequities, homelessness, direct (medical gap fees) and indirect cost (e.g. transport and parking, health literacy levels) [8, 37, 51-59]. The NP uses a type of "Health-Navigator" [63] brokering model appropriate for mental and physical health referrals and fills the decade or more gap in health service delivery not addressed by current homeless agencies, and the mainstream healthcare system.

Our scoping study proved the intervention can directly improve children's health outcomes. The consistency of engagement with health services is likely to have considerable flow-on effect to the children's overall wellbeing, education, and welfare. Funding from the Channel 7 research grant would allow us to evaluate the NP intervention providing data on the unmet physical, developmental and mental health needs of children in housing instability, capturing their complex histories and referral pathways (USAID referral tracking measures [47]), to modify the initiative were appropriate and to up-scale it throughout the state.

The potential pool of 250 families per month will provide for extensive data collection and referral follow-up.

JUSTIFICATION OF BUDGET – Word limit: 350

In-kind contribution will come from the Biostatistician and all academic staff allocated to the project (Level E x3; Level C x2; Level B x1) and from ISHS UCWB for appointment administration, equipment e.g. transport and caseworker support. CI's SEM, Odds Ratio analysis and narrative analysis ongoing analysis and final report writing.

We request funding to employ 1x Research Assistant at 0.6FTE @HEO5 step 01 for 12 months. The Research Assistant will be dedicated to overseeing the project, organising the Research Reference Group, Team meetings, Stakeholder meetings, synthesis of the findings from all areas of data collection and collecting data in the field e.g. interviews. RA interviews with parents, staff, and managers. Qualitative and quantitative data collection, preparation, and analysis.

NP data collection @HEO7 step 01. The Nurse Practitioner will collect data on the severity of the presenting condition, referral linkage and mapping, and referral follow up. These research activities are central to the research project and not covered by Medicare.

Interview incentives to families participating in RA face-to-face interviews (via Teams, Skype etc) (Total \$1,000, \$50 vouchers x 20 families)

To maximise the accuracy of the research findings from the intervention we will employ **professional transcription services**.

Transcription interviews of the NGO staff's assessment of the NP intervention (Total \$1,650)

1 hour of interview transcription @ rate \$2.75 per audio minute i.e. \$2.75/minute x 60min x 10 interviews equalling 600 hours. This price will ensure a timely file/transcription turn around

Transcription costs of 20 Parent interviews, as above totalling \$3,300

The above resources will enable CI Dr Yvonne Parry to dedicate her time to the project management, data collection, report writing, supervision and dissemination of the research findings. All CIs (given their extensive experience) will dedicate their time to the success of this project.

Dissemination: Video, \$3,000

In kind infographics, newsletters (in-kind), publications in journals, and conference presentations (Keynote speakers, Webinars, ACCYPN, ICCHNR).

Publicity of project on UCWB website, Flinders University, Caring Futures Institute, and internationally in the UK and WHO by team members in accordance with all Channel 7 directives, contracts, and policies.

Please supply evidence of your institution's employment on-cost calculation.

The Flinders University on-costs are in accordance with the link provided below.

<https://staff.flinders.edu.au/content/dam/staff/pc/salary-rates/sa-oncosts-jan-2020.pdf>